

EFFECTIVE URBAN GOVERNANCE FOR CITY MANAGEMENT AND SUSTAINABILITY IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study seeks to understand urban governance and its relationship with city sustainability by identifying problems associated with poor governance while recommending strategies that promote effective governance for sustainability. It reviewed relevant literature on governance, urban problems and sustainability issues in the Nigerian context and presenting the findings in tables and chart. The study reveal that cities face significant governance gaps due to weak institutional frameworks, corruption, inadequate community and private sector participation limiting transparency and accountability. Administratively many governments lack experts who understand use of economic flows and social outcomes in managing cities leading to increased slums, poor infrastructure, abandoned projects, water and air pollution, low employment and increased crime. The adoption of collaborative governance and urban political ecology strategies will effectively improve urban governance as it increases community and private sector participation fostering collaboration among all levels of governments. This leads to protection of vulnerable groups and the environment, improving urban sustainability as different groups have their socioeconomic and environmental interests addressed. There are challenges to using these strategies but constant dialogue, programme monitoring and interfacing will help improve these strategies for the socioeconomic and environmental sustainability of Nigerian cities.

Keywords: Urban Governance, Sustainability, City Sustainability.

Introduction

Man's fate on earth is tied to how well he can manage the resources available to him now and in the future. Our urban areas being engines of growth and development becomes increasingly imperative that they are managed sustainably. This is where effective governance comes into play in managing the environment and resources of Nigeria's urban entities. Urban governance and sustainability are therefore crucial issues in contemporary Nigeria as urbanization and population growth continue to strains city resources and infrastructure.

Nigeria as a country face rapid urbanization with an urban population projected to reach 70% by 2050 (UN-Habitat, 2022). Effective governance ensures equitable resource distribution, infrastructure development and environmental resilience now and in the future. However, cities continue to face challenges like weak institutions, informal settlements and climate vulnerability that continues to undermine a sustainable urban future (Adelekan, 2020). Many cities in Nigeria struggle with environmental management issues as weak governing institutions and frameworks continue to impede effective management. Poor waste management, inadequate infrastructure, slum generation, flooding and unplanned urban growth continue to threaten sustainability and quality of life of citizens in many Nigerian cities. The objectives of the study include,

- Understanding the causes of ineffective urban governance in Nigeria.
- Identifying problems associated with poor urban governance in Nigerian cities.
- Recommend strategies for promoting effective governance and city sustainability.

Conceptual Framework

Urban Governance: This is a concept referring to the mode of applying and implementing policies and plans that is intended to improve the social, economic and environmental wellbeing of urban areas through government instruments. The UN-Habitat (2015) however sees it as referring to the processes and structures through which cities are managed following these key elements,

- Institutional framework.
- Stakeholder participation.
- Transparency and accountability.

Many cities in Africa have governance structures and even legislative assemblies but are not effective in meeting the needs of citizens even as enormous resources are expended each year. Effective governance is critical for achieving any sort of sustainability which encompasses environmental, social and economic dimensions (World Bank, 2018). To achieve environmental sustainability, emphasis should be made on climate adaptation as well as effective management of urban resources. For social sustainability to be achieved attention should be given to affordable healthcare and inclusive housing while economic sustainability cover issues like job creation and circular economy (World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987).

Sustainability: The World Commission on Environment and Development (1987) states that sustainability is “meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (p. 43). This definition underscores the importance of balancing the economic, social and environmental considerations to ensure long term viability of those attributes that ensures man’s survival on earth for the longest possible period. It creates a “dynamic process for achieving balance between human and natural systems” (Kemp & Martens, 2007, p. 5), which is why sustainability should be at the heart of every development.

City Sustainability: The city is a complex space dealing with various interrelated flows and networks which people are exposed to as they try to fulfil current and long term goals. Therefore it is important that they continue to get those things that help them to fulfill life’s goals not just for them but for future generations. Haughton (1999) sees city sustainability as “the ability of a city to maintain and improve the wellbeing of residents, while reducing its ecological footprints and ensuring environmental, social and economic resilience (p. 62). However a city is said to be sustainable according to the UN-Habitat (2015¹) when it is able to create systems in ways that helps it achieve economic prosperity, social equity and environmental protection.

Theoretical Framework

The study adopts the theories of collaborative governance and urban political ecology. Collaborative governance theory (Ansell & Gash, 2008) emphasizes multi-stakeholder collaboration and inclusive decision-making in urban governance as it includes preferably all sections of society in meeting city goals. This approach can enhance environmental justice by incorporating diverse perspective and addressing power imbalances (Bulkeley & Mol, 2003).

Urban political ecology theory examines how power relations shape urban environment and access to resources (Swyngedouw & Heynen, 2003), revealing how urban governance can perpetuate

or challenge environmental inequalities. Both of these theories according to Agyeman & Evans (2004) suggests that effective urban governance and sustainability require addressing power dynamics and promoting inclusive environmental justice.

Overview of Urban Governance and Challenges to City Sustainability in Nigeria.

Nigerian cities hardly meet the needs of citizens and are not developing sustainably as officials often see office as means of enriching themselves. This leads to corruption and neglect, that cause increase in slum settlements, poor infrastructure, abandoned projects, poor refuse disposal systems, excessive air and water pollution, low employment rates and crime and it seems that governments are bereaved of ideas to tackle these situation. There is direct link between effective urban governance that is critical for cities to be sustainable and governments’ response to the needs of residents in managing resources efficiently and addressing environmental and social challenges (UN-Habitat, 2015). Ogundele et al. (2020) reveal that Nigerian cities face significant governance gaps that include weak institutional frameworks, inadequate community engagements and limited transparency and accountability. It is also observed that experts who can use economic flows and social outcomes are lacking in offices making it difficult for the resources plowed into managing cities to have any impact and increasing the problems currently facing cities.

Ineffective urban governance in Nigeria causes poor infrastructure, unplanned urban growth and reduced resources (Adewoyin, 2018), lowering economic productivity and reducing how sustainable cities can be. This is compounded by weak institutional frameworks, official corruption as well as limited capacities of urban governments in Nigeria (World Bank, 2018). Agunbiade et al. (2021) found that overlapping mandates between federal, states and local governments create policy conflicts, as witnessed in Lagos where Lagos State Urban Renewal Agency (LASURA) clashed with federal housing policies leading to uncoordinated slum upgrades (Oluwasegun, 2024). A 2025 report by Transparency International ranked Nigeria 154/180 in its Corruption Perception Index as 30% of urban infrastructure budget is misappropriated. Nigeria had always grappled with official corruption causing resources meant for infrastructure to be diverted as many projects are left uncompleted.

Table 1: Corruption and urban services delivery in Lagos.

Indicator	Lagos	African average	Source
% of infrastructure budget lost to corruption.	30%	18%	Transparency International (2025).
Days to obtain building permit.	120	45	World Bank (2023).
Public trust in local governments.	22%	48%	Afrobarometer (2025).

Note: Data reflects Lagos’s governance inefficiencies compared to regional peers.

Electricity access is still a consequential part of Nigeria’s underdevelopment with many urban areas having 12 hour daily outages (Adenikinju, 2025). Also it is observed that neighbourhoods in Owerri

Imo state go for days without electricity reducing resident's quality of life. The World Bank (2023) reports that only 10% of Nigerian cities have functional public transport with 40% of urban roads regarded as being in disrepair due to government neglect. Port Harcourt's water crises is very high as about 75% of residents rely on private vendors due to pipeline vandalism even as it is in an oil rich state (UNDP, 2023). Poor traffic management continues to retard progress of cities as PWC (2025) reveals that Lagos traffic crises accounts for \$1billion losses in cost of productivity, fuel waste \$300million and healthcare cost \$200million.

Figure 1: Breakdown of annual losses due to traffic crises in Lagos in percentages.

Note: Data from PriceWaterhouseCooper (PWC) (2025).

In Figure 1, \$200million indicate pollution related health expenses and is 15% of total costs of traffic crisis, suggesting that pollution significantly impacts on public spending likely covering treatment for pollution induced illnesses, health-care infrastructure or preventive measures. The amount include direct medical costs, lost productivity and long term care expenses to pollution exposure. Pollution is a major problem affecting city sustainability in Nigeria and the W.H.O. in 2025 listed Onitsha amongst the most polluted cities as a result of industrial emissions and open waste burning. In the case of Port-Harcourt the UNDP (2023) links oil spills in Ogoniland to a 50% decline in fishing livelihoods pushing many especially youths to poverty and urban crimes.

Poor land administration is a huge problem in cities as ineffective governance makes it difficult to administer urban land resources for the benefit of all. The UN-Habitat (2010) reveal that African cities are not just plague by poor governance and corruption many in city planning administration are people with strong physical planning background. This makes it difficult for them to look beyond physical development neglecting to apply economics, commodity flows, globalization and new governance strategies to city administration. This reduce benefits of living in cities as evidenced in the mass of street traders and urchins inundating streets often resulting in damage to public facilities reducing their lifespan and efficiency. Another phenomenon that continues to affect urban areas in Nigeria is flooding as it is now intractable. NIMET (2025) attributes 80% of urban flooding to neglect of drainages and wetland encroachment. The 2024 Kano floods displaced 500,000 people causing around \$200million in damages (NEMA, 2025).

Continuous urban sprawl and slum generation are result of ineffective urban planning and development control. An example is Makoko slum that houses over 300,000 people without access to proper sanitary facilities (UN-Habitat, 2023). A 2025 study of the Nigerian Urban Reproductive Health Initiative (NURHI) revealed that 60% of slum dwellers live in single-room units with five or more occupants that increases disease spread (Nwosu et al., 2026). Problems associated with ineffective governance affecting housing does not only deal with the poor and proliferation of slums but Nigeria’s elites too have been known to circumvent planning policies. The Federal Capital Territory’s audit in 2024 showed that 45% of buildings violate zoning laws as many elites continue to convert green spaces to residential and housing estates (FCDA, 2024).

Table 2: Slum population in three settlements in Lagos and their access to urban facilities.

Settlements	Population	% access to clean water	% with proper sanitation
Makoko	300,000	12%	8%
Ajegunle	500,000	18%	15%
Ototo-Gbame	75,000	5%	3%

Source: UN-Habitat (2023), Lagos Slum Atlas.

Ineffective urban planning and zoning arrangements and regulations with little inputs from urban dwellers regarding the best approaches to provide amenities will continue to make cities difficult places to live in. This study believes that if urban administrators fully collaborate with citizens and NGOs many of the pressing challenges can easily be dealt with.

Table 3: Collaborative governance in Nigerian cities (Strategies and outcomes).

Strategy	Description	Examples in Nigeria Cities
Inclusive decision making.	Involve communities, NGOs and private sector in urban planning.	Lagos State’s participatory budgeting process (World Bank, 2018).
Multi-level governance.	Foster collaboration between local, state and federal governments.	Abuja’s urban planning collaboration with federal agencies (Adewoyin, 2018).
Participatory budgeting.	Encourage citizen participation in budgeting.	Kaduna State’s budget transparency initiatives (Ogundele et al., 2020).

Table 4: Urban Political Ecology in Nigerian Cities (Environmental Justice Concerns).

Environmental Issue	Vulnerable Population	Examples in Nigerian Cities
Unequal access to green spaces.	Low income communities.	Limited parks in Lagos informal settlements (Agyeman & Evans, 2004).
Air pollution.	Urban poor.	Port-Harcourt’s oil pollution affecting local communities (Swyngedouw & Heynen, 2003).

Inadequate waste management.	Marginalized neighbourhoods.	Abandoned waste in Abuja’s low income areas (Adewoyin, 2018).
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These strategies have shown certain level of success in some states that have applied them as exemplified by Lagos, Abuja and Port-Harcourt but still have challenges as inputted in Table 5.

Table 5: Challenges of applying collaborative governance and urban political ecology to Nigerian urban governance.

Challenges	Description	Authors
Institutional fragmentation.	Overlapping responsibilities among government agencies under collaboration.	Akinola 2018.
Limited civic engagement.	Low citizen participation in urban planning and decision making.	Ibrahim & Oluwaseun 2019.
Power dynamics.	Powerful actors dominate decision making, marginalizing vulnerable groups.	Nwankwo & Ogbuefi 2020.
Resource constraints.	Limited funding and technical capacity limit sustainability initiatives.	Ezeah & Roberts 2018.

There are several limitations to applying collaborative governance and urban political ecology in the Nigerian context. There is the contextual relevance to prevailing local environment as Akinola (2018) believes that both strategies may not fully account for Nigerian cultural and political nuances. Also Nigeria’s level of data compilation and retrieval systems regarding sensitive issues are not very reliable as Ibrahim & Oluwaseun (2019) observed that data on urban governance and environmental issues are still difficult to retrieve making it difficult to analyze successes and progress of these strategies. It is therefore important that for maximum benefits cities should come up with strategies that suit their peculiar settings.

Recommendations

The study projects that urban governance can be improved for city sustainability through the following recommendations,

- Push for community led initiatives in areas where communities have records like in Lagos’s waste-to-energy initiatives that is shown to have improved urban environment.
- Institute policies for accountability and transparency to greatly improve governance by allowing citizens follow progress of policies and make vital inputs in real time.
- Create avenues that prioritize environmental justice in urban planning ensuring equitable accessibility to urban facilities to both wealthy and poor neighbourhoods.
- Strengthen the collaboration of public-private and public-community partnerships in the provision and maintenance of basic facilities to increase their protection and lifespan.
- Using smart planning techniques such as climate-smart planning that can integrate flood-risk maps into urban designs for environmental protection (Nwokocha, 2026).
- Integrate proven global practices that can be replicated locally, removing dependence on governments, like Kenya’s Kisumu Informal Settlement Programme that provided 10,000 affordable housing units through community cooperatives (UN-Habitat, 2023).

- For land administration urban governments can use Geographic Information Systems (GIS) an important tool for land-use monitoring for effective management (Okafor et al., 2024).
- Some decision-making authority can be transferred to local governments and communities, enabling for more responsive, closer and tailored service delivery (Adewoyin, 2018).
- The World Bank (2018) calls for performance measurement that uses proven indicators and metrics to evaluate performance of urban services and hold governments accountable.
- Market-oriented approaches that leverage private sector resources and expertise to deliver urban services and infrastructure has long been advocated by Osborne & Gaebler (1992).

Summary

- Effective urban governance is important as it promotes urban sustainability.
- Corruption and poor policy implementation cause urban problems such as slums increase, pollution, abandoned projects, traffic crises, poor infrastructure and unemployment.
- In some situations, government officials rely too much on physical planning as opposed to using socioeconomic tools that brings better results to enhance city management.
- There is evidence that about 30% of infrastructure budget is lost to corruption in Nigeria.
- In Lagos poor traffic management accounts for \$1billion loss in cost of productivity.
- 80% of urban flooding is due to government neglect of drainages and mismanagement of wetlands that negatively impacts city sustainability.
- Access to clean water and sanitation is very low in many neighbourhoods in Nigeria with some areas in Lagos having access to only 5% of clean water and 3% to proper sanitation.
- Promoting collaborative governance and urban political ecology theories are strategies that involve communities and NGOs in governance for better results helping to protect vulnerable communities and environment from harsh government policies and reforms.
- The strategies allows for market oriented approaches to be leveraged as private sector resources and expertise can help governments deliver and maintain critical urban services.
- The strategies use performance measurement with proven indicators to evaluate government actions to sustainability issues to gauge their effectiveness.
- Challenges of applying both strategies in the Nigerian context include duplication of responsibilities by governments and NGOs, low citizens' participation due to lack of awareness that may reduce their effectiveness and poor funding that limits technical capabilities of critical initiatives. These challenges can be overcome through constant dialogue, monitoring of programmes progress and interfacing with critical stakeholders.

Conclusion

Ordinarily cities are complex entities requiring critical attention for them to continue playing roles as engines of growth and development. However, if the administrative structures are weak and ineffective, cities become difficult to grow and develop sustainably. The threat posed by ineffective governance to Nigeria's socioeconomic and environmental sustainability is therefore a major concern that needs to be addressed headlong and decisively if our urban future is to be secured. Weak and ineffective urban governance and the challenges highlighted in this study are surmountable if the recommendations are strictly adhered to and implemented. Therefore, Nigeria's urban sustainability hinges on governance reforms, eradication of corrupt practices in governance, active citizens'

participation, private sector involvement, adaptive technology for local solutions, critical infrastructure development and promoting environmental resilience strategies for present and future generations. These changes and reforms will take time as all the challenges cannot be tackled in the immediate term but adopting evidence-based policies as well as global best practices will inevitably create grounds for meeting the goals of urban sustainability for Nigerian cities

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